

DIRECT COMPENSATION MANAGEMENT AS CORRELATE OF TEACHER TASK PERFORMANCE

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Abstract:

This study investigated direct compensation management and task performance of teachers in the Public Secondary Schools in Imo State, Nigeria. The purpose was to determine the influence of direct compensation management on the teachers' task performance in public secondary schools. Three research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. A sample of 664 teachers was selected from three education zones by proportional stratified sampling. Systematic sampling was used to identify the individual sample subjects. Data was collected with a researcher constructed questionnaire titled, "Direct Compensation Management and Teacher Task Performance Questionnaire (DCMTTPQ)", with a reliability coefficient of 0.816. The research questions were analyzed using weighted means and standard deviation while Pearson's Product Moment Correlation was used to analyze the hypotheses. The results revealed that irregular payment of teachers' salaries and allowances reduced to a great extent the teachers' task performance. It also revealed that there is a high and negative correlation between direct compensation management in Imo State public schools and the teachers' task performance. Based on the findings and conclusion, it was recommended that Imo State Government should be more committed to the welfare of teachers by paying their salaries and allowances as at when due in order to enhance their task performance. The paper also recommended the immediate implementation of 26% of annual budget allocation to education as recommended by UNESCO at both the Federal and State levels to meet up with the demands of teachers' direct compensation management.

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Keywords: direct compensation, irregular salaries, irregular allowances, teachers' task performance

1. Introduction

Compensation can be defined as all of the rewards earned by employees in return for their labour. This includes direct and indirect compensation (Hoare, 2013). Direct compensation consists of pay received in the form of wages, salaries, allowances, bonus and commissions provided at regular and consistent intervals (Numan, 2010; Hoare, 2013). Indirect compensation is referred to as benefits. Employee benefits are non-financial forms of compensation offered in addition to cash salary to enrich workers lives. Employee benefits are not performance based rather they are membership based (Decenzo and Robbins, 2007). Workers receive benefits regardless of their performance. Although employees benefits as a whole have no direct effect on employee performance, inadequate of it do contribute to low job satisfaction level, increase in absenteeism and turn over in employees (Decenzo and Robbins, 2007). Indirect compensation includes, good accommodation, provision of transportation distribution of some cell phones and some food items at the end of the month or year. A well designed compensation as well as benefits plan help to attract, motivate and retain talents in an organization (Numan, 2010).

Today humans are regarded as one of every profit making and non-profit making organizations' assets; consequently, they need to be efficiently and effectively managed. Compensation in human resources refers to the give and take relationship between the employer and the employee in monetary terms. The employee gives the service and receives pay from the employers. A well thought out compensation management goes a long way to not only motivate the employees but also improve the organizational effectiveness. This is more so when the direct compensation is enjoyed by the employee as at when due.

The focus of this paper is on irregular payment of salaries and allowances or irregular payment of direct compensation since it has direct effect on job performance of employees. This irregular payment of direct compensation involves delay of payment of salaries from one month to several months and the delay of payment of promotion and annual leave allowance from one year to several years. Salary is the most traditional form of wage which involves a certain amount of money over a specified period. The frequency of payment is another aspect of the compensation based on the standard of the organization. In some developed countries such as United Kingdom, United States, France and others pay per hour of service is used to compensate unskilled and some skilled labourers. In Nigerian daily pay is practiced only with respect to unskilled

labour. For skilled labour such as professionals in Nigeria, salaries are paid at the end of every month. This also applies to the teachers' salaries. The frequency of meeting this obligation by the employer in the public institutions seems to be a difficult issue in Nigeria. Payment of salaries to workers in public institutions is hardly regarded as a priority. It is the general belief that education is not a profit making enterprise in Nigeria hence the annual budget allocation to education wavers between 4 and 11 percent between 1999 and 2013 against the United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organizations (UNESCO) demand of 26%. Table 1 shows the Federal annual budgetary allocation to education from 1999 to 2013 (Micaiah, 2013).

Table 1: Federal Government Budgetary Allocation to Education in Nigeria by Year

S/N	Year	Percentage
1	1999	4.47
2	2000	8.73
3	2001	7.14
4	2002	6.91
5	2003	7.76
6	2004	5.25
7	2005	10.43
8	2006	9.75
9	2007	10.04
10	2008	8.79
11	2009	7.37
12	2010	9.32
13	2011	9.86
14	2012	10.21
15	2013	8.28

Source: <https://www.slideshare.net/satisence/budgetary-allocation-to>

The politicians would prefer to spend huge sums of money on projects that do not contribute to the well-being of the people even when they are complaining of inadequate funding from Federal Government. As noted by Adegoke (2016) one of the states owing several months allocation of teachers' salaries found it necessary to spend N600 million on state Christmas decorations. The president of the Nigerian Union of Teachers (NUT) also in a workshop on commercialization and privatization of education revealed that 28 states owed teachers backlog of salaries (Ikpefan, 2017). Table 2 shows the distribution of the number of months salaries are owed to teachers by some of these states.

Table 2: Arrears of Teachers' Salaries Owed by some States despite Bailout

S/N	State	Arrears of Salaries owed in Months
1	Abia	6 (oral interview)
2	Bayelsa	7
3	Benue	4
4	Ekiti	6
5	Imo	6
6	Kogi	15
7	Kwara	11
8	Nasarawa	3
9	Ogun	6
10	Osun	12
11	Ondo	7
12	Oyo	6

Source: www.Vanguardngr.com Ahiuma-Young, Akinyemi, Johnson, Ajayi, Obalopo, Nkwopara, Duru (2017).

In some states where salaries are presumed to be regularly paid only 70% or less of their salaries are made available to them without any explanation (oral interview 2017). Series of incessant industrial actions have been carried out by the teachers without any appreciable improvement on salary and allowances payment (Effiong, 2016, Oyibode, 2017). The arrears of teachers' salaries and allowances have ranged from a few months to several months and a few years to several years respectively. As a result of this irregular payment of salaries and allowances teachers promotions are usually not accompanied by any cash rewards in recent times, such promotions are said to be notional. The Federal Government recently gave bailout funds twice to states including Imo State, to off-set the salary arrears, this still did not reflect in the payment of direct compensation, teachers were still being owed salaries for several months and allowances for several years (Odu, 2015; Premium Times, 2017; Omotayo (ND). Ozigi, Ndu and International Labour Organization (ILO) in Ofoegbu (2004) pointed out that teacher motivation is very low and should be enhanced for better educational results.

In Nigerian school systems, female teachers dominate unlike in the sixties and seventies. This poor management of direct compensation has driven many male teachers out of the profession as they cannot fulfil their financial obligation to their families. It is observed that virtually all the teachers in recent times have other trades they practice in order to meet their needs. These range from farming, trading, taxi driving or organizing extra lessons for students for a fee. Because of the immediate rewards the teachers get from their other trades, it is generally believed that they tend to pay more attention to them than their primary professional assignment. Direct compensation is a motivation for teachers as rightly stated by Ofoegbu (2004), with

motivation teachers' pedagogical and management roles would be enhanced and translated with effective attainment of educational goals. Unfortunately, this divided attention resulting from poor management of teachers' direct compensation is presumed to have some effect on the task performance of teachers. The situation of direct compensation management in most Nigerian states and the consequent response of teachers is not different from what operates in Imo State. Teachers in Imo State in addition to being owed salaries have been receiving 70% of their salaries as far back as February 2016 and no form of financial allowances in the past six years has been paid to them (oral interview 2017). It is therefore necessary to investigate how the irregular payment of teachers' salaries and allowances impact on their task performance.

Several studies have been carried out on the use of compensation at work. Taiwo (1984) carried out a study on incentives and teachers performance in Ibadan and found that the level of teachers performance become high with the introduction of bonuses in cash and allowances by the state Government. Earlier, Ejiogu (1983) carried out a study in Lagos and found that cash bonuses improved performance. Hoy and Miskel (1987) in their studies found a relationship between payment of salaries among others and teacher performance. Okoli (2009) investigated the effectiveness of motivational strategies of incentive and fear as factors in teachers' performance in secondary schools in Abia and Anambra States in Nigeria. The results showed that incentive motivational strategy enhances teachers' performance. Ahukanna (2010) also investigated the strategies for re-branding secondary school teachers for better performance in Owerri educational zone Imo State Nigeria using a descriptive survey. The results revealed among others that adequate and regular salary payment as well as regular payment of allowances among others could motivate teachers to perform better at their tasks. Ofoegbu (2004) also found that teachers would be adequately motivated if salaries were paid regularly while the teacher motivation would improve the quality and standard of the school system. The purpose of this paper is to determine the extent to which direct compensation management is a correlate of teacher task performance.

2. The Problem

An employee is entitled to his salary and allowances as soon as the stipulated time for payment reaches. Where these salaries and allowances are paid and regularly too the worker will be motivated to attend to his or her task effectively and efficiently. Imo State just like many other States in Nigeria has the culture of not paying teachers as at when due and this may not end soon. Teachers in public secondary schools are worse off for it because politicians do not see education system as a money yielding venture

from which they can benefit. Consequently, it has been very difficult for Nigeria to raise education budget to 26% of the total budget as stipulated by UNESCO.

This culture of owing teachers' salaries and allowances for several months pushed many public school teachers to turn to other private means of earning a living to survive, doing everything from farming, taxi driving to petty trading thus paying little or no attention to their primary assignment. This has ended up leaving many state-run schools without the full attention of professionals. The consequent effect on students particularly the final year students who have to sit for external examinations is better imagined than experienced. Students are taught at the whims and caprices of the teacher sometimes students have two classes in a whole day. This has led many parents and guardians to turn to private institutions they can hardly afford. With the issues raised above, the researcher saw the need to investigate direct compensation management as a correlate of teacher task performance to facilitate the revival of public secondary schools in Imo State.

3. Theoretical Framework

The theory on which this study is based is the expectancy theory. This theory is concerned with the relationship between behavior and performance level. For instance if teachers perceive that intensive effort by them in implementing the curriculum will improve teachers' performance, the expectancy will be high. Expectancy is the extent to which an individual believes that a given level of activity will result in a specific level of goal achievement. Valence on the other hand is the importance an individual attaches to a reward or incentives. This implies that the degree of attractiveness an individual attaches to a reward or incentive such as regular payment of salaries, promotion allowance and annual leave allowances will attract a commensurate performance. In other words where the teachers are paid regularly they would attach a great importance to their tasks and this will motivate them to perform their tasks diligently knowing full well that something good will come their way at the end of the month.

However where they have low expectation towards the rewards where they are paid many months in arrears, they would lose interest in the reward and consequently decline in their job performance.

4. Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions;

1. To what extent does irregular payment of salaries influence teachers' task performance in Imo State public secondary schools?

2. What is the extent to which irregular payment of promotion arrears affect teachers' task performance in Imo State public secondary schools?
3. To what extent would irregular payment of teachers' leave allowances influence teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State?

4.1 Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide this study at $P < 0.05$ level of significance:

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between irregular payment of teachers' salaries and teacher task performance.

H0₂: There is no significant relationship between irregular payment of promotion allowance and teachers' task performance.

5. Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Imo State was the area of study. There are 288 public secondary schools in Imo State divided into three educational zones. The population of study was 6,641 teachers. The three educational zones had the following population of teachers respectively Okigwe 1032, Orlu 1286 and Owerri 4323 with the population being a few thousands 10% of the total population was used in the study which is 644 (Nkwocha, 2007). Proportional stratified sampling was used to determine the various sample sizes while systematic sampling technique was used to identify the individual sample subjects in the three zones. The instrument for the study was a researcher constructed questionnaire titled "Direct Compensation Management and Teacher Task Performance Questionnaire (DCMTTPQ)". The instrument was structured under the three clusters of irregular payment of salaries, promotion allowances and leave allowances. The response mode ranged from very low extent (VLE), Low Extent (LE), High Extent (HE) to Very High Extent (VHE). The lowest value being VLE had 1 point while the highest value, VHE had 4 points. The Cronbach alpha coefficient was used to establish the internal consistency of the instrument which was 0.816. Descriptive statistics such as means and standard deviation were used to analyze the research questions while Pearsons Product – Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to analyze the hypotheses.

6. Results

6.1 Research Question 1: *"To what extent does Irregular Payment of Salary Influence Teachers' Task Performance in Imo State Public Secondary Schools?"*

Table 3: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Extent to which Irregular Payment of Salaries Influence Teachers Task Performance

S/N	Item	$\bar{X}$	SD	Decision
	To what extent:			
1	does irregular payment of teachers' salaries enhance their being regular in class to teach?	1.93	0.875	VLE
2	does non-payment of salaries as at when due motivate teachers willingness to show concern for their students in the teaching and learning process?	1.62	0.762	VLE
3	does irregular payment of teachers' salaries make them complete their tasks on schedule?	2.01	1.02	LE
4	does non-payment of salaries as at when due encourage teachers to take on more tasks?	1.42	0.80	VLE
5	does irregular payment of salaries encourage the teachers to deliver effective lessons?	1.34	0.89	VLE
	Pooled mean	1.664	0.87	VLE

The analysis on table 3 shows that irregular payment of teachers' salaries enhanced to a very low extent teachers regularity in class ($\bar{X} = 1.93$). This means that the irregular payment of teachers' salaries reduced to a large extent their enthusiasm to be regular in class. The result also shows that irregular payment of salaries to a very low extent teachers to willingly show concern for their students in the teaching and learning process, ($\bar{X} = 1.62$). The irregular payment of salaries to teachers also lowered to a great extent their enthusiasm to complete their tasks on schedule, ($\bar{X} = 2.01$). The result also shows that irregular payment of teachers' salary it lowered to a large extent the encouragement for teachers to take on new tasks, ($\bar{X} = 1.42$). It also lowered to a very large extent the encouragement for teachers to deliver effective lessons ($\bar{X} = 1.34$).

In summary the pooled mean ($\bar{X} = 1.66$) indicates that teachers task performance is lowered to a great extent by irregular payment of salaries.

6.2 Research Question 2: *“What is the Extent to which Irregular Payment of Promotion Allowance affect Teachers Task Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Imo State”?*

Table 4: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Extent Irregular Payment of Promotion Allowances Influence Teachers Task Performance

S/N	Item	$\bar{X}$	SD	Decision
1	To what extent: do promotion allowances when not paid as at when due discourage diligent marking of students assignments by teachers?	3.20	1.08	VHE
2	do promotions without financial backing encourage the teachers willingness to work?	1.32	0.94	VLE
3	do irregular payment of promotion allowances influences teacher student relationship positively?	1.63	0.81	VLE
4	do irregular payment of promotion allowances encourage teachers lesson preparation?	1.35	0.92	VLE
5	do delayed payment of promotion allowances encourage teachers to be innovative in the classroom?	1.67	0.93	VLE
	Pooled mean	1.67	0.93	VLE

On Table 4 item 1 indicates very high discouragement in diligent marking of students assignment as result of non-payment of promotion arrears as at when due, ($\bar{X} = 3.20$). Item 2 shows that promoting teachers without any cash backing to a very low extent encouraged the teachers willingness to work, ($\bar{X} = 1.32$). Item 3 shows that irregular payment of promotion arrears, to a very low extent influenced a positive teacher/student payment relationship, ($\bar{X} = 1.63$). Item 4 shows that irregular payment of promotion arrears to a very low extent encourages teachers to prepare their lessons, ($\bar{X} = 1.35$). Item 5 shows that delayed payment of promotion arrears to a very low extent encourages teachers to be innovative in the classroom. The pooled mean ($\bar{X} = 1.67$) indicates that the irregular payment of promotion arrears of teachers influenced to a very low extent teacher task performance among teachers.

Research Question 3: *“Would Irregular Payment of Teachers Annual Leave Allowances Influence Teachers Task Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Imo State?”*

Table 5: Mean Responses of Teachers on the extent of Irregular Payment of Annual Leave Allowances Influence on Teachers Task performance

S/N	Item	$\bar{X}$	SD	Decision
	To what extent:			
1	does irregular payment of teachers annual leave allowances prevents them from making sacrifices to assist the school in preparation for new intake during holidays.	3.47	1.53	VHE
2	does irregular payment of teachers leave allowances affect the dedication of the teachers caring for the students.	3.20	1.41	VHE
3	does carrying out instructions from the head of department is influenced by delayed payment of teachers' annual leave allowances.	2.84	0.92	HE
4	does regular payment of annual leave allowance improves teacher diligence at work.	2.71	0.86	HE
5	is annual leave allowance regarded as additional earning for teachers by which any delay in its payment reduces the teachers concentration on the task performance involved in the job.	3.40	1.30	VHE
	Pooled mean	3.12	664	Accepted

The results on Table 5 show that the mean responses on all the items were above 2.5. This indicates that all the items influence teacher task performance. Item 1 indicates that delayed payment of teachers annual leave allowances prevented them from making sacrifices during the holidays to assist the school in preparation for new intake to a very high extent ($\bar{X}$ 3.47). Item 2 shows that irregular payment of teachers leave allowances to a very high extent affected the dedication of the teachers in caring for the students ($\bar{X}$ = 3.20) Item 3 shows that the delayed payment of teachers annual leave allowances to a very extent influenced the teachers willingness to carryout instructions from the heads of their departments, ($\bar{X}$ = 2.84). Item 4 indicates that regular payment of annual leave allowances to a high extent improved teachers diligence at work, ($\bar{X}$ = 2.71). Item 5 shows that annual leave allowances to a very high extent is regarded as extra earnings by teachers and therefore reduced the teachers concentration on the task performance involved in the job when delayed ($\bar{X}$ = 3.40). The pooled mean ($\bar{X}$ = 3.12) indicates that teachers task performance to a very high extent influenced by the irregular payment of annual leave allowances.

Hypothesis 1

H0: There is no Significant Relationship between the Irregular Payment of Salary and Teachers' Task Performance in Public Secondary School in Imo State.

Table 6: Relationship between Irregular payment of Salaries and Teachers' Task Performance

Irregular payment of salary	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	Irregular payment of salary	Teachers' task performance
		1	-0.756**
	N	664	0.000
Teachers Task Performance	Pearson Correlation Sig (2 – tailed)	-0.756**	1
	N	644	644

** Correlation is significant at 0.05 level 2-tailed

Table 6 shows the correlation value of -0.756 and p-value of -0.756 and p-value of 0.00.

The results on Table 6 show that there is a high negative relationship between irregular payment of teachers salary and teachers task performance - .756 at 0.01. The higher the irregular payment of teachers' salary the lower the teachers' task performance. The negative value is quite high which shows that this relationship is a very strong one. The p-value being less than the level of significance indicates a rejection of the null hypothesis.

Hypothesis 2:

H0₂: There is no Significant Relationship between Irregular Payment of Teachers Promotion Allowances and their Task Performance in Public Secondary School in Imo State.

Table 7: Relationship between Irregular payment of Promotion Allowances and Teacher's Task Performance

Irregular payment of salary	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	Irregular payment of salary	Teachers' task performance
		1	-0.763**
	N	664	0.000
Teachers Task Performance	Pearson Correlation Sig (2 – tailed)	-0.763**	1
	N	644	644

Correlation is significant at 0.05 level 2-tailed.

From the table $R^2 = -0.763$, P-value = $0.000 < 0.05$ consequently the null hypothesis is rejected since the p-value 0.000 is less than the level of significance, 0.05.

Table 7 shows the result of the correlational analysis between irregular payment of promotion allowances and teachers task performance. The table shows that there is a high negative correlational relationship between irregular payment of allowances and teachers task performance -0.763 , $p < 0.05$. This relationship implies that the higher the irregular payment of promotion allowances the poorer the teachers' task performance. This negative value is also quite high which shows that the relationship is a very strong one.

7. Discussion of Findings

The main objective of this study was to examine the extent to which direct compensation management is a correlate of teacher task performance. This study revealed that irregular payment of teachers' salaries or non-payment of teachers' salaries as at when due reduced to a very low extent their attendance to classes as well as the teachers' concern for their students in the teaching and learning process respectively. This agrees with the findings of Taiwo (1984) and Okoli (2009) that teachers' performance is influenced by incentives which motivate them. This implies that if the salaries were paid as at when due the teachers professional task would be given the desired attention. The results also revealed that the willingness of the teachers to complete their tasks on schedule and their readiness to take on more tasks would be very low if the salaries were irregularly paid. This also agrees with the findings of Hoy and Miskel (1987) who found a relationship between payment of salaries and teacher performance. This implies that if there was regular payment of salaries, teachers would be very willing to complete their tasks on schedule as well as be encouraged to take on more tasks.

The results also showed that the teachers' readiness to deliver effective lessons would be at its lowest ebb if the salaries were paid irregularly. This also agrees with the findings of Ahukanna (2010) who also found that regular payment of salaries motivates teachers' task performance. In other words if teachers were paid as at when due the teachers would be eager and willing to deliver effective lessons. This is because the teacher already knows that at the end of every month, he would be able to meet his family needs, and his own personal needs as his pay would always be released to him intact. But where the salaries were irregularly paid, they would not be able to meet their family needs and consequently there would be no motivation to perform any tasks. In general, the result shows that irregular payment of teachers' salaries reduces the task performance of the teachers while the corollary is also the case.

The results also showed that when promotion arrears were not paid as at when due it discourages diligent marking of students assignments by teachers to a very high

extent. This agrees with earlier findings of Okoli (2009), this can be explained by the fact that teachers look at the various allowances as additional earnings which could be used to solve some family problems. But when such is not forthcoming, they can be some discouragement or mistrust on the part of the teacher which would subsequently influence how he or she handles the profession in terms of task performance. The results also show that promotion without financial backing encourages teachers to a very low extent to willingly go to work as well as maintain a positive teacher student relationship. This could be explained by the fact that the morale of the teachers would be greatly lowered by the poor motivation of irregular payment of promotion allowances. This also agrees with the expectancy theory where the expected reward comes in the form of irregular salary, which the teacher regards as unimportant because of the way it is managed and would accordingly respond to it in the same way. The teacher might be seeing the students as a bunch of nuisance if the reward is not valued. The results also show that the irregular payment of promotion allowances encouraged to a very low extent teacher lesson preparation and the teachers' innovative nature in the classroom. This agrees with the findings of Ahukanna (2010) that adequate and regular payment of allowances could motivate teachers to perform better at their tasks. This can be explained by the fact that any teacher that cannot meet up with his or her financial obligations to the family would feel inadequate and angry when he or she leaves his or her home every day to work like any other person. This state of mind can never make somebody creative and such a person can hardly fully concentrate while preparing the lesson note for the next day. These results generally indicate that the irregular payment of promotion allowances to teachers to a very high extent influence teachers task performance. This agrees with the corollary findings of Ahukanna (2010) that regular payment of allowances motivates teachers to perform better at their tasks.

Further findings of the study indicate that irregular payment of teachers' annual leave allowances to a very high extent prevented them from making sacrifices to assist the school in preparation for new intake during holidays. This also agrees with the findings of Taiwo (1984), Ejiogu (1983) and Ahukanna (2009) that payment of cash allowances raises the level of teacher's performances. In other words, where this cash payment of allowances is not forthcoming, it will lower the enthusiasm of the teachers to perform their duties. This can be explained by the fact that in a developing economy like Nigeria the majority of the people are still grappling with the basic needs of life such as food, shelter, and clothing and when money is not available for these basic needs for someone who goes to work each day with the hope to earn a living there is a strong demoralization with its attendant individual responses. This could definitely make the teachers not wanting to make sacrifices to help the school make preparations for new entrants during the holidays. The results also showed that irregular payment of

leave allowances to a very high extent lower the dedication of the teachers in caring for the students. This could be explained by the fact that teachers who felt their services were not recognized and rewarded would never be willing to render extra service by caring for the students outside the academic work. The results also showed that regular payment of annual leave allowances improves teacher diligence at work. This agrees with the findings of Ahukanna (2010) that regular payment of allowances to teachers could make teachers perform better at their work. This can be explained by the fact that once the basic needs of the teachers were satisfied they would be able to concentrate on their performance knowing that they need not worry where and when the next meal would come.

The results also show that the teachers highly agree that the leave allowances were additional earnings for them and any delay in its coming would jeopardize their concentration on their tasks. This also agrees with the findings of Taiwo (1984) to Okolo (2009) and Ahukanna (2010) that payment of cash bonuses and allowances improve teachers' task performance. This can be explained by the fact that a teacher who is not sure of when his next meal would come and has turned to other trades such as farming, trading, taxi driving in which the reward is instant cannot have enough time to attend to his or her primary assignment of which he or she is not sure of when the reward would come.

The findings of this study also revealed that there is a significant high and negative relationship between irregular payment of salaries, promotion allowances and teachers' task performance. The greater the irregularity of the payment of salaries and promotion allowances the poorer the task performance of teachers. This agrees with the findings of Hoy and Miskel (1987) that there is a significant relationship between payment of salaries and teacher performance. This is explained by the fact that the essence of people taking up a job is to earn a living and when such a job is done there should be a reciprocal gesture of a reward when that is not done the job suffers. The results also show that the greater the irregularity of teachers direct compensation the less their task performance. This is explained by the fact that where direct compensation is irregular there is no motivation and less importance will be attached to the reward which eventually affects the task performance.

8. Conclusion

In line with the findings of this study, it is concluded that the management of direct compensation is crucial to task performance of teachers in Imo State public secondary schools. Teachers being the major assets in the education industry must have their direct compensation efficiently and effectively managed to get the best results from the

teachers' task performance. This when adhered to will lead to organizational effectiveness in schools.

9. Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study the following recommendations were made:

Some generalizations were made based on the fact that 28 out of 36 states are involved in this irregular payment of salaries and allowances.

1. Nigerian politicians should realize that education system is a service delivery outfit that produces manpower for the nation and should be treated with the importance it deserves.
2. The Federal and State government should as a matter of urgency implement the allocation of 26% of their total annual budget to education sector being a minimum recommendation by the United Nations Education Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). By so doing the states will gain some more money from the federal allocation as well as generate more funds within the state for education and will have no excuse but pay the teachers their salaries and allowances as at when due.
3. Imo State government should show some commitment towards the payment of teachers' salaries and allowances as at when due to motivate them in their task performance. This should also apply to all state governments that are in this category of irregular payment of teachers' salaries and allowances since education is the key to nation building and no nation can rise above its quality of education.
4. The Federal Government should establish a devoted monitoring team to oversee the payment of salaries of teachers at the state level to prevent possible diversion of education funds to other sectors. This will stimulate same level of accountability.
5. The Federal government should ensure that no state government short pays teachers in terms of their actual salaries. They must be paid their exact salaries. Any state government indulging in that should have its statutory allocation withheld, until all such monies are refunded in full.

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